

Structure of Phenanthraquinoneimide Anhydride—Some New Transformations

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The structure of phenanthraquinoneimide anhydride (PQIA), is confirmed to be 10 H-dibenzo (c, e)-phenanthro-(9', 10' : 4, 5)-imidazo (1, 2-a) azepine-10-one. A refluxing solution of PQIA in methanolic potassium hydroxide gave an amorphous insoluble acid which was confirmed to be 2'-(1 H-phenanthro-[9, 10-d]-imidazol-2-yl)-2-biphenyl carboxylic acid by spectral analysis and comparison with authentic sample. Decarboxylation of this acid resulted in the formation of 2-biphenyl-phenanthrimidazole which was indirectly synthesized.

Phanquone on treatment with ammonium acetate-acetic acid gave phanquinic acid similar to the transformation observed in case of phenanthraquinone.

VERY recently the structure of phenanthraquinone-imide anhydride (PQIA), product arising from phenanthraquinoneimine on thermolysis is shown to be 10 H-dibenzo (c,e) phenanthro-(9',10' : 4,5)-imidazo (1,2-a) azepine-10-one¹. All the earlier structures proposed²⁻⁴ for PQIA have been shown to be incorrect. The essential feature of the recent¹ work aims at the construction of the azepinone ring in a two step process (Scheme-1). The condensation involving 2-2'-diformyl biphenyl with phenanthraquinone has no direct precedence and consequently the characterization of the product (II) obtained in low yield is not unambiguous. Nevertheless our present work when combined with that of barton and Grinham leaves little doubt that PQIA has the assigned structure (I).

Scheme 1

Examination of the structure of PQIA reveals the presence of an activated carbonyl group which could, in principle, undergo a facile ring opening reaction with nucleophiles. This characterization is in good agreement with the reported transformation of PQIA with nucleophile like hydroxide². The interesting aspect of these reactions are that they could be easily reversed to

PQIA by thermal means. All these factors suggested the operations of a rather facile ring opening-ring closure process. It was then planned to use the ring opening reaction effectively to obtain products which could be unambiguously synthesized.

The reaction of PQIA with saturated methanolic potassium hydroxide gave an amorphous white solid which was identified as an insoluble acid. The insolubility of this acid in common organic solvents precluded further purification. A recent survey of

Scheme 2

literature⁸ reveals the formation of such a compound (m.p. 320-322°) from the reaction of phenanthraquinone with ammonium acetate in glacial acetic acid. This information further gave us added evidence for the ring opened product of PQIA to be 2'-(1-H-phenanthro[9,10-d]imidazol-2-yl)-2-biphenyl carboxylic acid (III). Work was designed to decarboxylate (III) to 2-biphenyl phenanthrimidazole (V), which could be indirectly synthesized following the procedure of Steck and Day⁹. Decarboxylation of the acid (III) in copper-quinoline gave crystalline material having the expected molecular formula $C_{27}H_{18}N_2$ which was synthesized in an unambiguous manner (Scheme-2). The key intermediate 2-formyl biphenyl (IV) was prepared⁷ from 2-iodo biphenyl by the reaction of the corresponding Grignard with N-methyl formamide. The aldehyde (IV) on treatment with phenanthraquinone and ammonium acetate gave (V) in excellent yields. The synthetic sample obtained was identical in all respects with that of the decarboxylated product (mixed m.p., super impossible IR) obtained by us earlier. This finding further gave us strong proof for the structure of PQIA.

Having achieved our objective in view, attempts were directed towards synthesis of identical systems analogous to PQIA. Condensation of phanquone (VI) with ammonium acetate in glacial acetic acid resulted in the formation of a base soluble product which was identified as (VII) on the basis of IR and analysis. The IR peak for the carbonyl group in (VII) in the region 1665-1675 cm^{-1} reveals that it has got hydrogen bonding with the imidazole hydrogen (N-H). This yellow crystalline acid on treatment with acetyl chloride-pyridine gave (VIII) with the appearance of a strong peak at 1675 cm^{-1} corresponding to a imide carbonyl group. The intensity of this peak is, however, very strong compared to the carbonyl of the carboxyl group in (VII). The absence of the diffused absorption in the region of 3600-2700 cm^{-1} in (VIII), strongly indicates that cyclization has occurred. Again, the same product could also be obtained by cyclization of the acid with refluxing *o*-dichloro benzene solution. Although the IR spectrum of both the compounds are superimposable, to our surprise the m.p. of both were found to be different. This may be attributed to the formation of

the one and same compound from two different origin. Further the lowering of the m.p. in case of the latter reaction may possibly attributed due to the penetration of the solvent system into the crystal lattice. The mixed m.p. of the system, however, is dramatically not lowered down. The IR peaks of both the products were similar to PQIA (I). Further the product (VIII) on treatment with saturated methanolic potassium hydroxide in the condition of (I)→(III) change gave the analogous acid a light yellow compound, which gave a positive test for a carboxyl group (vide infra). The structure of this product is tentatively assigned as (VII) (Scheme-3).

All these reactions led us to believe that systems analogous to PQIA, having an azeponone ring system could be constructed in a convenient way and the interesting transformations could be achieved.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillaries in a WISWO melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. The IR spectra were run in KBr pellets on Perkin-Elmer-137 Infra-red spectrophotometer.

Phenanthraquinoneimide anhydride (I) :

A *o*-dichloro benzene solution of phenanthraquinoneimine⁸ (4.0 g, 0.02 mol, 15 ml) was distilled slowly during over-night to enable removal of water. The hot mixture was cooled, diluted with petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°), (?0 ml), filtered and the residue refluxed in methanol/chloroform (1:1, 20 ml) to remove the unreacted phenanthraquinoneimine. The crude anhydride was crystallised from pyridine and dried to give 0.965 g (25%) of (I), m.p. 260-261° (lit.⁸ m.p. 257°). IR : ν_{max}^{KBr} 1712 (C=O), 1441, 1323 and 921 cm^{-1} .

Reaction of (I) with saturated methanolic potassium hydroxide : Isolation of 2'-(1-H-Phenanthro[9,10-d]imidazol-2-yl)-2-biphenyl carboxylic acid (III) :

A suspension of (I) (0.5 g, 0.0012 mol) in saturated methanolic potassium hydroxide (5 ml) was stirred over-night at room temperature and then refluxed for 1 hr. The reaction mixture was cooled, treated with hydrochloric acid (6N, 15 ml), the precipitated acid filtered, washed several times with water and dried *in vacuo* to give 0.42 g (70%) of the acid as a white amorphous solid, m.p. 318-320° C (lit.⁸ m.p. 320-322°). IR : ν_{max}^{KBr} 3000-2500 (diffused absorption) 1667 (C=O) cm^{-1} .

Decarboxylation of (III) with copper/quinoline : Isolation of (V) :

A mixture of (III) (0.3 g, 0.0075 mol), copper powder (0.15 g, 0.025 mol) and freshly distilled quinoline (5 ml) was refluxed at 240-250° for 2 hrs. The suspension was poured into ice, extracted with ether and the ethereal extract washed several times with water and dil. HCl. The combined aqueous layer when allowed to stand over-night deposited crude (V) (0.065 g) which on crystallisation from benzene/hexane gave 0.035 g

SCHEME 3

(20%) of the pure imidazole, m.p. 230° (Found : C, 87.64; H, 5.07; N, 7.38%; Calcd. for $C_{27}H_{18}N_2$; C, 87.56; H, 4.86; N, 7.08%. IR : ν_{max}^{KBr} 1610, 1455 and 1445 cm^{-1} ; MS : m/e 370; UV : λ_{max}^{EtOH} (ϵ) : 357 (2716), 340 (2808), 303 (8045), 284 (18025), 257 (68307) and 229 (32250) nm.

Reaction of phenanthraquinone with 2-Formyl biphenyl :

Synthesis of (V) :

A solution of phenanthraquinone (0.52 g, 0.0025 mol) and ammonium acetate (3.88 g, 0.0025 mol) in hot glacial acetic acid (5 ml) was treated with 2-formyl biphenyl⁷ (0.545 g, 0.003 mol) in 5 ml of acetic acid. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 1 hr., cooled, diluted with water (40 ml) and neutralised with liquor ammonia. The precipitate was collected, crystallised from benzene/hexane to give 0.85 g (92%) of (V) m.p. 223-224° IR : ν_{max}^{KBr} 1610, 1455 and 1445 cm^{-1} ; UV : λ_{max}^{EtOH} (ϵ) : 356 (2734), 341 (2842), 305 (8072), 285 (18074), 257 (68368) and 229 (32288) nm.

This compound was identical in all respects (m.p. IR and UV) with the decarboxylated product.

Preparation of (VII) from Phanquone (VI) :

Phanquone (4.2 g, 0.02 mol) and ammonium acetate (3.08 g, 0.02 mol) were refluxed in glacial acetic acid (30 ml) for 1 hr. The solution was cooled, neutralised with liquor ammonia. The yellow crystalline precipitate filtered, washed several times with water and dried to give 4.9 g (63%) of (VII), m.p. 288°. (Found : C, 68.65; H, 3.13; N, 19.88; Calcd. for $C_{24}H_{14}N_2O_2$; C, 68.89; H, 3.34; N, 20.09%) IR : ν_{max}^{KBr} 3600-2700 (diffused adsorption due to monomeric -COOH and sec. amine), 1675-1665 (C=O) cm^{-1} .

Cyclization of (VII) to (VIII) with Acetyl chloride-Pyridine :

To a stirred and cooled solution of (VII) (2.35 g, 0.006 mol) in pyridine (30 ml) was added acetyl chloride (2 ml). The solution was allowed to warm to ambient temperature and was further stirred for an additional 2 hr. Dilution with water (100 ml) gave a light yellow precipitate which was collected and dried to give 1.08 g (47%) of (VIII) m.p. 316° (Found : C, 71.82; H, 2.76; N, 20.92; Calcd. for $C_{24}H_{12}N_2O$; C, 72.00; H, 3.00; N, 21.00%) IR : ν_{max}^{KBr} 1675, 1580, 1430, 1010 and 795 cm^{-1} .

Cyclization of (VII) to (VIII) in refluxing o-dichloro benzene :

A o-dichloro benzene solution of (VII) (1 g, 0.0025 mol) was refluxed for 10 hr. The hot mixture was

cooled, diluted with petroleum ether, the precipitated solid was filtered and dried to give 0.48 g (42%) of (VIII) m.p. 280° (Found : C, 71.72; H, 2.84; N, 20.84; Calcd. for $C_{24}H_{12}N_2O$; C, 72.00; H, 3.00; N, 21.00%) IR : ν_{max}^{KBr} 1675, 1580, 1420, 1010 and 795 cm^{-1} .

Reaction of (VIII) with saturated methanolic potassium hydroxide :

Isolation of (VII) :

A suspension of (VIII) (0.39 g, 0.001 mol) in saturated methanolic potassium hydroxide (5 ml) was left stirred over-night refluxed for additional 1 hr., cooled and neutralized with 6N HCl (15 ml). The resulting light yellow precipitate was filtered, washed with water, dried to give 0.28 g (75%) of (VII), m.p. 291° (Found : C, 68.76; H, 3.28; N, 19.94; Calcd. for $C_{24}H_{14}N_2O_2$; C, 68.89; H, 3.34; N, 20.09%) IR : ν_{max}^{KBr} 3600-2700 (diffused adsorption due to monomeric -COOH and sec. amine), 1675-1665 (C=O) cm^{-1} . The mixed m.p. of this product with that obtained from phanquone did not show any depression.

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